

THE FUNCTIONAL – SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF TRANSITIVE VERBS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564077>

Samieva Lobar Nasriddin qizi

Master student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Paluanova Khalifa Daribaevna

Scientific advisor: Ph.D. (DSc), dotsent

UzSWLU

Annotation: *Transitivity is an important grammatical issue and has been a hot topic in linguistic theories. It has been studied from different approaches. This article aims to describe the main features and propositions about transitivity in the view of different theories*

Key words: *transitive verb, intransitive verb, object, prepositional verb, monotransitive complementation.*

O`TIMLI FE`LLARNING FUNKSIONAL SEMANTIK TAHLILI

Samiyeva Lobar Nasriddin qizi,

O`zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti magistranti

Paluanova Xalifa Daribayevna

Ilmiy rahbar: F.f.d. (DSc), dotsent

O`zDJTU

Annotatsiya: *O`timlilik muhim grammatik masala bo`lib, tilshunoslik nazariyalarida dolzarb mavzu bo`lib kelgan. U turli xil yondashuvlardan o`rganilgan. Ushbu maqola turli nazariyalar nuqtai nazaridan o`timlilik haqidagi asosiy xususiyatlar va takliflarni tasvirlashga qaratilgan.*

Kalit so`zlar: *o`timli fe`l, o`timsiz fe`l, to`ldiruvchi, predlogli fe`l, monotransitiv to`ldiruvchi.*

ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНО – СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ПЕРЕХОДНЫХ ГЛАГОЛОВ

Самиева Лобар Насриддин кизи

Магистр Узбекского государственного университета мировых языков

Палуанова Халифа Дарибаевна

Научный руководитель: Ph.D.(DSc), доцент

УзГУМЯ

Аннотация: *Переходность является важным грамматическим вопросом и была актуальной проблемой в лингвистических теориях. Его изучали с разных точек зрения. В этой статье основное внимание уделяется описанию ключевых особенностей и предположений о транзитивности с точки зрения различных теорий.*

Ключевые слова: *переходный глагол, непереходный глагол, дополнение, предложный глагол, моно переходное дополнение.*

Grammatically the verb is the most complex part of speech. This is due to the central role it performs in the expression of the predicative functions of the sentence, i.e. the functions establishing the connection between the situations (situational event) named in the utterance and reality. The complexity of the verb is inherent not only in the intricate structure of its grammatical categories, but also in its various subclass divisions, as well as in its falling into two sets of forms profoundly different from each other: the finite set and the non-finite set. The complicated character of the grammatical and lexico-grammatical structure of the verb has given rise to much dispute and controversy.

Verbs can also be classified from the point of view of their ability of taking objects. In accord with this, we can distinguish two types of verbs: **transitive** and **intransitive**. The former type of verbs are divided into two:

a) verbs, which are combined with direct object: *to have a book, to find the address;*

b) verbs, which take prepositional objects: *to wait for, to look at, talk about...*

To the latter type the following verbs are referred:

a) verbs expressing state: *be, exist, live, sleep, die...;*

b) verbs of motion: *go, come, run, arrive, travel...;*

c) verbs expressing the position in space: *lie, sit, stand... .*

In many cases, we come across an intermediate stratum. We find such stratum between transitive and intransitive verbs, which is called **causative** verbs, while verbs intransitive in their origin, but sometimes used as **transitive**: *to fly a kite, to sail a ship, to nod approval...* The same is found in the construction "**cognate object**": *to live a long life, to die the death of a hero...* Now, let's see the examples taken from William Shakespeare's comedy:

To live long life in the western isles

Of Kernes and Gallowglasses is supplied;

And fortune, on his damed quarrel smiled.

Verbs appearing in subtypes of monotransitive complementation:

1. Some very frequent passivisable simplex verbs in monotransitive use: *begin, believe, bite, bring, call, carry, close, cut, describe, desire, do, doubt, enjoy, expect, feel, find, follow, get, hear, hold, keep, know, lead, like, lose, love, make, marry, mean, meet, mind, move, need, obtain, pass, produce, receive, remember, require, say, see, start, study, support, take, use, visit, want, wash, waste, watch, win, etc.*

2. Monotransitive complementation by noun phrase as direct object (simplex verbs)

a. Verbs with a typically animate subject + a typically concrete (inanimate object): *carry, clean, cover, eat, examine, lower, see, stop, throw, watch, win, and write.*

There were no white dunes covered with reddish grass beyond them: there was nothing to mark.

Distaining Fortune, with his brandished steel, which smoked with bloody execution, like Valour's minion... (W. Shakespeare)

b. Verbs with a typically animate subject + either concrete or abstract (inanimate) object: *abolish, cover, define, discuss, explain, forget, invent, lose, report, rule, utter.*

"I forget exactly, but I said to myself at that time."

c. Verbs with a typically animate subject + typically animate object: *admire, beat, despise, flatter, hug, kill, kiss, meet, reject, respect, ridicule, support.*

Carved out his passage, till he faced the slave;

Which ne'er shook hands, nor bade farewell to him...

d. Verbs with a typically concrete or abstract (inanimate) subject + animate object: *affect, appeal, bother, deceive, fascinate, grieve, incense, please, satisfy, surprise, trouble, upset.*

3. Monotransitive complementation by noun phrase as prepositional object with:

a. prepositional verbs: *account for, concentrate on, look after/at/on/to, add to, conform to, object to, adjust to, consent to, part with, admit to, contribute to pay for, agree with/on/to, deal with, pray for, aim at/for, decide on, preach, about/on, allow for, dwell (up)on, provide for, apply for, enlarge (up)on, quarrel about/with, argue about, hear about/of, read about, arrange for, hint at, refer to, ask for, hope for, rejoice at, attend to, insist on, rely on, interfere with, resort to, call for/(up)on, learn about, run for, care for, lecture about/on, speak about/on, comment on, listen to, take to complain about, live on, think about/of, conceive of, long for, wish for.*

"Christ, I think of you all day."

"No, I don't believe in God."

Till he unseamed him from the nave to the chaps,

And fixed his, bead upon our battlements. (W. Shakespeare)

b. phrasal-prepositional verbs marks verbs as being passivisable: *break in on, keep away from, catch up on, keep up with, check up on, look down on, come down with, look out for, cut down on, look up to, do away with, put up with, get away with, stand up for, get down to, turn out for*

4. Monotransitive complementation by finite **wh-clauses** as objects:

Verbs normally occurring in a nonassertive context are marked [NA]. Some verbs are part of negative or predominantly negative construction when combined with the wh-interrogative clause: *not care, not mind, can't fathom, can't tell, argue, arrange, ascertain, ask, beware, calculate, care, check, choose, confirm, consider, decide, demonstrate, depend, discover, doubt, enquire, explain, express, fathom, guess, hear, imagine, indicate, inquire, judge, know, learn, make out, mind, note, observe, ponder, predict, prove, realize, remember, say, see, show, tell, think, wonder.*

5. Monotransitive complementation by **wh-infinitive clauses** as objects: *arrange, ask, calculate, check, choose, consider, demonstrate, discover, discuss, enquire, establish, explain, find out, forget, imagine, indicate, judge, know, learn, note, notice, observe, perceive, remember, say, see, show, tell, think and wonder.*

6. Monotransitive complementation by subjectless **to-infinitive clauses** as direct objects include the following semantic classes of verbs. Verbs marked 1 also occur with the subjectless **-ing** clauses, those marked with 2 also occur with to-infinitives with a subject:

a. emotive verbs of liking and disliking: *dread_{1,2}, hate_{1,2}, like_{1,2}, love_{1,2}, prefer_{1,2}*

b. aspectual verbs (of beginning, continuing, ending): *begin₁, cease₁, commence₁, continue₁, start₁*

"His hair is distinctly greyer since this began."

And at more time, The interim having wighed it, let us speak Our free hearts each to other. (W. Shakespeare)

c. retrospective verbs: *forget₁, remember₁, regret₁*

"How on earth did you ever get to know him?" I asked.—

"Oh, it was years ago. Six years, seven years, I forget."

If it were done when, it is done, then't were well

If were done quickly: if the, assassination... (W. Shakespeare)

d. *choose₁, hope, intend_{1,2}, mean_{1,2}, need₁, plan₁, propose₁, want_{1,2}, wish₂*

The windscreen wiper scraped away the seconds as he saw the dawn of a new hope.

Could trammel up the consequence and catch,

With his Surcease success, that but this blow... (W. Shakespeare)

e. deign, disdain₁, help_{1,2}, scorn₁, venture₁

There was no help for it.

Could trammel up the consequence and catch

With his surcease success; that but this blow. (W. Shakespeare)

f. ask, beg, demand, offer, promise, refuse, swear, undertake, vow, jump

"How on earth did you ever get to know him?" I asked. —

"Oh, it was years ago. Six years, seven years, I forget."

Might be the be-all and the end – all here...

We'd jump the life to come. (W. Shakespeare)

g. affect, claim, profess₁

"Why!" said Arabella, affecting dismay.

"You've promised to marry me several times as we sat here tonight."

From this moment, The very firstlings of my heart shall be,

The firstlings of my hand. (W. Shakespeare)

h. afford₁, attempt₁, contrive, endeavour, fail, learn, manage, neglect, omit, try₁

7. Some prepositional verbs taking to-infinitive clauses without subject as complements arranged in appropriate semantic groups (ix. was added as a miscellaneous class):

a. emotive verbs of liking and disliking: long (for)₂, ache (for), aim (for)₂, aspire (to), burn (for), burst (for), (not) care (for), clamour (for)₂, itch (for)₂, yearn (for)₂

b. retrospective verbs: bother (about)_{1,2}, condescend (to), hesitate (about)₁,

c. agree (to/on/about)₂, assent (to), consent (to)

d. pretend (to)

e. strive (for), seek (for)

f. arrange (for)_{1,2}, decide (on)₁, resolve (on)₁, prepare (for)₁, serve (for)₁

8. Monotransitive complementation by subjectless -ing clauses as direct objects. Superscript 1 indicates that the verb also takes -ing clauses with subjects, and superscript 4 indicates that perfective construction, is possible:

a. emotive verbs: (can't) bear₁, detest₁, dislike₁, dread, enjoy, (not) fancy₁, hate₁, like₁, loathe₁, love₁, (not) mind₁, miss₁, regret_{1,4}, relish₁, resent₁, (can't) stand₁

b. aspectual verbs: cease, commence, continue, quit, resume, start₁, stop₁

c. admit₄, avoid, confess₄, consider, deny₄, deserve₂, discourage_{1,3}, envisage_{1,3}, escape, forget_{1,3,4}, (can't) help₁, involve_{1,3}, justify_{1,3}, need_{1,2}, permit_{1,3}, recall_{1,3,4}, recommend_{1,3}, remember_{1,3,4}, repent, require₂, risk_{1,3}, save_{1,3}, try, want_{1, <dialectal 2>}

It is no wonder that **factual verbs** go with the indicative only, since they state facts, i.e. provide propositional information. They can be subdivided into two subtypes:

- a. public factual verbs
- b. private factual verbs

Public factual verbs consist of speech act verbs introducing indirect statements (or speech): *acknowledge, add, admit, affirm, allege, argue, assert, bet, boast, certify, claim, complain, confess, confirm, declare, deny, exclaim, explain, maintain, mention, predict, proclaim, promise, pronounce, reply, report, say, state, suggest, swear, testify, write.*

- a. *She acknowledged that she had been at fault.*
- b. *They boasted that they had never had an accident yet.*
- c. *Dad explained that we have to go to bed now because we need to get up very early in the morning.*

Some of these verbs may also occur with other complement types (1), or with that clauses as suasive verbs (2):

- (1) a. *He promised that they would come.*
- b. *He promised to come.*
- (2) a. *He suggested that everything was lost.*
- b. *He suggested that we should come earlier.*

Private factual verbs express intellectual states such as belief, and intellectual acts such as discovery. These are private in the sense that they are not observable: *accept, anticipate, assume, believe, conclude, consider, decide, deduce, demonstrate, determine, discover, doubt, dream, ensure, establish, estimate, expect, feel, find, forget, gather, guess, hear, hold, hope, imagine, judge, know, learn, mean, note, notice, observe, presume, presuppose, realize, recall, reckon, remember, see, show, signify, suppose, suspect, think, understand.*

- a. *I assume that you are in safety.*
- b. *He believes that all children are born with equal intelligence.*
- c. *I expect that it was an accident.*
- d. *Do you realize that this is the third time you've forgotten?*

Again, some of these verbs may also occur with other complement types.

Suasive verbs can be followed by a that-clause either with putative should, or with the mandative subject, while the indicative verb is found only in BrE:

Suasive verbs imply intentions to bring about some change in the future, whether or these are verbally formulated as commands, suggestions, etc. In other words, suasive verbs express directives (which may be either public or private, i.e. volition, desire): *agree, allow, ask, beg, beg, command, decide, decree, demand, desire, determine, enjoin, grant, insist, instruct, move, ordain, order, pray, prefer, pronounce, recommend, request, resolve, rule, suggest, urge, vote*. Once more, there is a great deal of overlap: some of these verbs may also occur with other complement types. The complex transitive pattern NP + to-infinitive is a common alternative to that-clauses with suasive verbs:

- a. *They intended that the news (should) be suppressed.*
- b. *They intended the news to be suppressed.*

There are two major views on the nature of transitivity. Whereas one view holds that a verb is either transitive or intransitive, the other posits that transitivity is a matter of degree, based on the functional relations established in language use. The functional account on the other hand showed that some intransitive verbs may become transitive in causative construction, causativity being a valency changing process.

REFERENCES:

1. Блох М.Я. Теоретическая грамматика английского языка. М.,2005
 2. Пыш В.А. The structure of Modern English. М-L.,1971
 3. Iofik L.L., Chakhoyan L.P. *Readings in the Theory of English Grammar*. Leningrad, 1972. 241-245 pp.
 4. Iriskulov M.A. Kuldashev A.M. Theoretical Grammar of the English Language. Tashkent, 2008, 208 pages
 5. Khudyakov A. Theoretical English Grammar. Moscow, 2007 (In Russian), 310 p.
 6. Качалова В.А. *Грамматика английского языка*. М., 2004
 7. Quirk R., Greenbaum S., Leech G., Svartvik J. A Grammar of Contemporary English. Lnd.,1972
-